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The bilingual math dilemma - Language switching costs in declarative and procedural arithmetic knowledge

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ABSTRACT

Language Switching Costs (LSC), characterized by slower and more error-prone responses when the language of encoding and retrieval differ, provide insights into the language-dependency of knowledge representations. A growing body of experimental research has revealed LSC in declarative arithmetic knowledge such as arithmetic facts. However, it remains unclear whether these costs extend to procedural arithmetic knowledge. Furthermore, the long-term stability of LSC has not been investigated, studies on their relationship with individual differences in cognitive competencies have yielded inconsistent results, and the cognitive processes underlying LSC are not fully understood yet. To address these research gaps, we trained 122 bilingual participants over four days on artificial arithmetic facts (declarative knowledge) and a novel arithmetic procedure (procedural knowledge) in either their first (L1) or second language (L2). Participants were tested on the trained material in both languages at four time points: 1 day, 1 week, 1 month, and 3 months after training. In all test trials, participants were required to indicate potential translation processes into the trained language and into Arabic digits. Results revealed LSC in reaction times for both declarative and procedural knowledge, persisting up to 3 months post-training. These findings, together with the results from the translation self-reports, suggest that both declarative and procedural arithmetic knowledge are language-dependent, which only partly agrees with triple code models on arithmetic. No associations between LSC and individual differences in cognitive competencies were observed. These findings are of both theoretical and practical relevance for bilingual knowledge representations in arithmetic.

1. Introduction

A growing body of research in cognitive psychology has demonstrated that certain types of knowledge are stored in a language-dependent way and that a switch of languages from encoding to retrieval results in measurable cognitive costs on performance. This phenomenon has been termed *Language-Switching Costs* (LSC). LSC regarding language dependent knowledge representations typically manifest in slower reaction times and lower accuracies when the language of retrieval and encoding differ compared to a condition where the language remains the same (Marian & Fausey, 2006; Marian &

Neisser, 2000; Spelke & Tsivkin, 2001). Most experimental studies on LSC have been conducted on declarative knowledge in arithmetic, which encompasses memorized facts such as the multiplication table. In these studies, learners first acquired declarative knowledge (e.g., new arithmetic facts) over multiple days in one language (their L1 or L2) and were then required to retrieve this knowledge in both languages (L1 and L2). Retrieval in the untrained compared to the trained language resulted in longer reaction times and/or lower accuracies, with the performance difference reflecting LSC. The aim of the present study is to extend this body of research by addressing the following research gaps. First, given the strong focus on declarative arithmetic knowledge in previous

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studies, it is unclear whether similar LSC emerge for procedural arithmetic knowledge (i.e., knowledge on the application of algorithms in problem solving). Second, since all previous studies administered only one posttest session after the training, we do not have any evidence yet on the stability of LSC over time, i.e., whether and to what extent they decrease after repeated retrieval of information in both languages. Third, there has been inconsistent evidence regarding the association of LSC with individual differences in related competencies (e.g., unreplicated correlations with L2 proficiency and executive functions, Volmer et al., 2018).

A general theoretical framework to explain LSC is the *Encoding Specificity Hypothesis* by Tulving and Thomson (1973). According to this hypothesis, information is closely linked to the context in which it was encoded. A mismatch of the context of encoding and the context of retrieval can thus result in cognitive costs, which manifest in poorer performance when retrieving information. This context comprises aspects such as background noise, taste, movement, even smell – but also language. In fact, there is a growing body of research that knowledge is represented in close connection to the language in which it was encoded and that cognitive costs emerge in situations where the language of retrieval does not match the language of encoding (Kempert et al., 2018; Marian & Neisser, 2000). Marian and Fausey (2006), for instance, taught participants academic-type fake information in the subjects History, Biology, Mythology and Chemistry monolingually in either English or Spanish. Afterwards, participants were tested on the trained content in both languages. They observed that participants could retrieve the information less accurately and more slowly when their language of encoding and retrieval did not match, thus reflecting LSC.

Most experimental research on LSC has been conducted in the domain of arithmetic, revealing consistent evidence of LSC for declarative arithmetic knowledge, in general, and arithmetic facts, in particular (Chen et al., 2016; Grabner et al., 2012; Hahn et al., 2019; Saalbach et al., 2013; Saalbach et al., 2016; Volmer et al., 2018). Arithmetic facts, such as basic multiplication table problems, are stored in long-term memory. There is substantial literature on the influence of language of learning and language experience for arithmetic facts (see Cerda & Wicha, 2023 for a recent review). In bilinguals, there is a typical performance advantage (faster (re-)production or verification) for the language of arithmetic learning (often L1) that may reflect differences in language experience rather than language-specific memory representations based on early learning. Bilinguals with higher proficiency in the non-learning language (often L2) show small or no performance differences across languages as compared to bilinguals with lower proficiency in the non-learning language (Garcia et al., 2021; for related electrophysiological findings cf. Salillas & Wicha, 2012).

Studies on LSC in arithmetic knowledge have typically required adult participants to learn new arithmetic facts (often through a multi-day training), either in their L1 or L2. Because single-digit basic multiplication tables are typically already stored in adults' memory, some studies used more complex multiplication or subtraction problems (e.g., multiplications with two-digit operands) as learning material (Hahn et al., 2025, 2019; Volmer et al., 2018). More recent studies devised artificial arithmetic fact learning tasks in which artificial equations need to be rote-learned (e.g. $16 \blacksquare 8 = 39$). These tasks offer the advantage that they cannot be solved through a known calculation procedure so it can be assured that problem-solving solely relies on fact retrieval. For example, Hahn et al. (2019) examined LSC for both actual and artificial arithmetic fact knowledge. They trained German native-speaking participants over four days six multiplication (e.g.: $12 \times 3 = 36$), six subtraction (e.g.: $48 - 13 = 35$) and six artificial problems ($16 \text{ box } 8 = 39$), either in German, the participants' L1, or in English, the participants' L2. On the subsequent day after training, participants were tested in both languages. Significant LSC in terms of slower reaction times were observed for all three types of fact knowledge, indicating that not only the artificial but also the novel actual arithmetic facts were stored in a language-dependent way.

In addition to declarative arithmetic knowledge of associations between operands and solutions (arithmetic facts), arithmetic cognition strongly relies on procedural knowledge (Ashcraft, 1992; Campbell & Epp, 2004). Procedural arithmetic knowledge involves algorithms and rule-based strategies such as carrying, borrowing, or multi-step transformations, or stated more generally, knowledge about how to solve an arithmetic problem. This type of knowledge appears to be even more critical than declarative knowledge as most arithmetic problem solving requires the application of calculation procedures. The two forms of knowledge differ not only in their cognitive characteristics but also in their sensitivity to language context.

In the area of mathematical cognition researchers have developed several theoretical models that can account for LSC such as the *Bilingual Encoding Complex Model* (BECM; Bernardo, 2001) and the *Bilingual Triple Code Model* (BTCM, Lachelin et al., 2023). The BECM is an adaptation of the *Encoding Complex Model* (Campbell, 1994; Campbell et al., 1999; Campbell & Clark, 1992; Campbell & Epp, 2004). The ECM proposes that arithmetic performance arises from the interaction of multiple encoding pathways that are specific to format and modality. These pathways connect problem representations to their corresponding answers through learned, experience-dependent associations. The model assumes distinct memory representations for Arabic digits and number words, with access efficiency—such as retrieval and reproduction—shaped by an individual's practice history. Because arithmetic facts are most often learned and practiced in Arabic digits, digit-based pathways tend to be the most efficient, followed by pathways in the learner's language of arithmetic. When the format or language of input and output does not match these dominant associations—for example, when retrieving facts in a different format or language than the one in which they were learned—performance costs arise. These costs reflect both reliance on weaker pathways and the need to resolve competition among simultaneously activated alternatives. The BECM extends the ECM by assuming at least three distinct memory codes in a bilingual's arithmetic memory (i.e., Arabic digit codes, verbal codes in L1 and in L2). These codes differ in strength and efficiency based on prior experience. The stronger of the two verbal codes is not always L1, but the language of learning and practicing arithmetic. Within this framework, asymmetries in translation and language switching can arise as a function of language dominance, proficiency, and task structure. Specifically, LSC originate either from using the weaker code (L2) or from converting the problem into the stronger code (L1), retrieving the answer, and then convert it back into the weaker code (L2). The activation across codes is asymmetric; that is, the weaker code (e.g., verbal code in L2) spreads activation to the stronger code (e.g., verbal code in L1) but to a smaller extent or not at all vice versa. Thus, the BECM predicts that switching from L2 to L1 would result in lower LSC than switching from L1 to L2.

Researchers recently introduced the BTCM (Lachelin et al., 2023) as an extension of *Triple Code Model* (TCM, Dehaene & Cohen, 1995; for a recent review see Siemann & Petermann, 2018). This BTCM comprises the same three kinds of representations as the TCM: *Analogue Magnitude Representation*, *Visual Arabic Number Form*, and *Auditory Verbal Word Frame* (see Fig. 1). The Analogue Magnitude Representation stores numerical information in the form of an abstract magnitude (e.g., “●●” for an entity of 2 objects). It usually is activated when approximate quantities need to be processed or exact arithmetic problems need to be calculated. The Visual Arabic Number Form stores numerical information as a sequence of Arabic digits (e.g., “2”) and is usually involved in calculations that span multiple digits. The major difference between the BTCM and the TCM concerns the Auditory Verbal Word Frame, which stores numerical information as a sequence of words (e.g., “two”). In the BTCM, the Auditory Verbal Word Frame is split into two sub-domains (see Fig. 1). These sub-domains represent bilinguals' two languages of mathematical learning. Their first language of mathematical learning is more strongly connected with the other domains of the BTCM – the Visual Arabic Number Form and the Analogue Magnitude

Fig. 1. Bilingual Triple Code Model (Lachelin et al., 2023). This Model is meant to be an expansion of the previous TCM (Dehaene & Cohen, 1995) by including a bilingual's primary (L(M)1) and secondary (L(M)2) language of mathematics education. Full lines symbolize stronger connections, dashed lines symbolize weaker ones.

Representation – compared to their second language of mathematical learning. A key mechanism for LSC in arithmetic fact knowledge is the need for translation between the two linguistic sub-domains within the Auditory Verbal Word Frame. According to Lachelin et al. (2023), this translation is expected to be faster from the second to the first language of mathematical learning than vice versa, which similarly to the BECM predicts a directionality of LSC; that is, lower LSC for switching from L2 to L1 compared to switching from L1 to L2. The empirical support for this theoretically assumed directionality is however mixed, with some studies finding directional costs (e.g., Saalbach et al., 2013), and others not (e.g., Hahn et al., 2019). Finally, the BTCM maintains the prediction of the original TCM that procedural knowledge should not be as susceptible to LSC as declarative knowledge because procedural knowledge relies more strongly on the two other less language dependent codes.

The BECM and the BTCM provide a strong theoretical framework for identifying and explaining the cognitive mechanisms underlying Language-Switching Costs (LSC). Within this framework, LSC in arithmetic fact retrieval can be attributed to reliance on weaker representational codes (as proposed by the BECM), the need to convert between codes (BECM), or direct translation between linguistic subdomains within the Auditory Verbal Word Frame (BTCM). The BTCM also accounts for the absence of LSC in tasks that do not depend on arithmetic fact retrieval – such as approximation tasks (e.g., Dehaene et al., 1999; Spelke & Tsivkin, 2001) – by positing the involvement of a language-independent Analogue Magnitude Representation.

Direct evidence on the cognitive processes underlying LSC, however, is scarce and mixed. Hahn et al. (2025) collected trial-by-trial self-reports from their participants on both, their problem-solving strategy (strategy report: asking whether they used fact retrieval or a calculation procedure) and the application of translation processes (translation report: asking whether they translated any numbers during problem solving). Hahn et al. observed LSC for multiplication, subtraction and artificial arithmetic facts. Moreover, they found that participants reported a substantially larger rate of translations (46 vs. 4%) in the language-switching (compared to the no-switching) trials and a slightly larger rate of calculation procedures (12 vs. 10%). Additionally, the extent of LSC in reaction times could only be predicted by translation processes and not by calculation procedures. These findings indicated that LSC emerge mainly due to translation or conversion processes (for similar results, see Venkatraman et al., 2006). In contrast, a functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) study by Grabner et al. (2009) indicated that LSC in new multiplication and subtraction facts were accompanied by increased activation in brain areas associated with magnitude processing, visuo-spatial imagery, numerical stimulus recognition, and executive functions. This finding suggested that LSC are

rather related to additional numerical information processing than to language translation processes. An fMRI study from Van Rinsveld et al. (2017) provided evidence that LSC may result from a potential reliance on a weaker code leading to weaker associative pathways between problems and solutions. They had bilinguals from Luxemburg calculate both simple and complex arithmetic problems. Luxemburg allows for a special case of bilingual research because its inhabitants start with German as the instructional language in school and switch to French in later school grades. During problem calculation, these bilinguals engaged their left superior temporal regions to a greater extent in German compared to French. These regions are supposed to support the association of number symbols or number words with their semantic representation. Based on these findings, Van Rinsveld et al. suggested a more direct semantic association between simple addition problems and their respective solutions in German, their first language of mathematics instruction, than in French, their second language of mathematics instruction. To sum up, evidence on the cognitive processes underlying LSC is mixed with studies, for example, pointing to underlying translation or calculation processes (e.g.: Grabner et al., 2012; Hahn et al., 2025) or semantic associations of differing strength between mathematical problems and solutions (e.g.: Cerda et al., 2024; Van Rinsveld et al., 2017).

A question that has not been addressed in previous research is the question of stability of LSC. Previous studies have relied on a single posttest session conducted shortly (typically on the next day after training; e.g., Saalbach et al., 2013). Therefore, it is unclear whether repeated retrieval in both languages reduces LSC. From a theoretical standpoint, two contrasting hypotheses exist. According to a stability hypothesis, LSC reflect structural properties of how knowledge is stored (i.e., tightly bound to the original encoding language), and therefore they should persist across time and practice. This hypothesis is supported by findings that arithmetic knowledge is strongly tied to the language of early mathematics learning, irrespective of later language dominance (Salillas & Wicha, 2012). Alternatively, according to an adaptation hypothesis, repeated retrieval in both languages may gradually strengthen cross-linguistic links, thereby reducing LSC as learners gain fluency in accessing knowledge from multiple linguistic codes. This hypothesis is in line with findings from research on retrieval practice (also called testing effect; Glaser & Richter, 2023; Rowland, 2014). Accordingly, with every retrieval process accessing that knowledge becomes easier. Consequently, retrieval in the untrained language should create novel knowledge representation in that language and, thus, reduce LSC with repeated retrieval (see also Wußing et al., 2023). In addition, the adaptation hypothesis conforms to the findings from Martinez-Lincoln et al. (2015) who tested bilingual teachers teaching

mathematics in their L2. In an arithmetic verification task, they found equivalent correctness-related ERPs in both languages (L1 and L2), indicating that via continued practice, retrieval efficiency benefits.

Finally, the existence of LSC as a mean sample-based effect raises the question whether there are individual differences which may make a person more susceptible to LSC. Based on a recent meta-analysis (Garcia et al., 2021), lower L2 proficiency is associated with larger differences in arithmetic task performance across languages. In line with this evidence, Volmer et al. (2018) reported negative associations of LSC with L2 language proficiency (i.e., higher language proficiency was related to smaller LSC). Additionally, they found a negative correlation with inhibition but no correlations with general intelligence and working memory. In two more recent studies, in contrast, correlations of LSC were neither observed with L2 vocabulary knowledge (Hahn et al., 2019), nor with intelligence and arithmetic skills (Hahn et al., 2025). Due to these mixed findings, further investigation of the relevance of individual differences for the emergence of LSC is needed. Given the cognitive mechanisms the above-mentioned models assume, individuals with higher L2 language proficiency should have a stronger L2 verbal code in arithmetic and perform better in conversion/translation processes across codes/languages, and individuals with better arithmetic skills may benefit from faster and more accurate arithmetic processing in the untrained language. Regarding domain-specific characteristics, executive functions may loom large. Better executive functions may allow individuals to switch faster between knowledge representations and more effectively suppress interferences from irrelevant language representations. These functions are also strongly associated with general intelligence, which should be further investigated.

1.1. The present study

Taken together, research has revealed robust LSC in declarative arithmetic knowledge (Grabner et al., 2012; Hahn et al., 2019; Hahn et al., 2025; Saalbach et al., 2013; Volmer et al., 2018), but leaves open critical questions about their generality, stability, individual moderators and underlying mechanisms. To answer these questions, we conducted an experiment in which participants underwent a four-day training of both declarative and procedural arithmetic knowledge. For declarative arithmetic knowledge, we presented participants with artificial arithmetic facts (*Box Arithmetic*, see Hahn et al., 2025, 2019), whilst for procedural arithmetic knowledge, participants were required to learn and apply a novel arithmetic procedure (*Pound Arithmetic*; Rickard, 1997). The training was administered in one of two training languages – either in participants' L1 (German) or L2 (English). In a posttest session on the day after the last training, the trained material was tested in both languages. In addition, participants were tested in both languages at three follow-up sessions (one week, one month and three months after the training), hence resulting in a total of four test sessions. After solving each problem in the test sessions, participants were asked to report (a) their solution strategy (strategy self-report: fact retrieval, calculation procedure, or other strategy) and (b) whether they translated the problem into their trained language, into a visual Arabic digit code or not at all (translation self-report). Before the experiment, participants were screened on a wide range of variables including language proficiency, mathematical abilities, executive functions and general cognitive abilities.

We examined the following research questions and hypotheses. First, do LSC emerge not only for declarative arithmetic knowledge but also for procedural arithmetic knowledge? Based on previous evidence and the two theoretical models (BECM and BTCM), we expected LSC in reaction times for declarative arithmetic knowledge, but not for procedural arithmetic knowledge. Second, are LSC stable across four posttest sessions distributed over 3 months after the end of the training? Third, what psychological variables moderate the strength of LSC? And, fourth, to what extent are translation processes into the trained language and into numerical representations reported in trials requiring language-

switching and those that do not?

2. Method

2.1. Participants

Our sample consisted of 122 balanced and unbalanced bilinguals (75 female, 2 diverse) aged between 18 and 35 years ($M = 23.41$, $SD = 4.02$) with German as their L1. Through the multi day nature of this study a certain drop out was observable with the sample getting smaller with each follow-up session: 114 participants (69 female, 2 diverse; Age: $M = 23.35$, $SD = 3.87$) at follow-up 1 (1 week after training), 97 participants (56 female, 2 diverse; Age: $M = 23.79$, $SD = 4.09$) at follow-up 2 (1 month) and 81 participants (54 female, 1 diverse; Age: $M = 23.85$, $SD = 4.31$) at follow-up 3 (3 months). Participants underwent a preliminary screening after which they qualified for this study if their test score in the Cambridge General English Questionnaire (Cambridge University Press and Assessment, n.d.) exceeded 17 points, signifying an English level of at least B2, according to the *Common European Framework for Reference* (CEFR, Language Policy Programme, 2020). The participants were randomly assigned to one of two groups. Half of them (60) received the arithmetic training in German (their L1), while the other half (62) received it in English (their L2). Later analyses revealed, that both groups were balanced both in their English levels and bilingual dominance. For their participation, participants received either 130€ or research credits for the psychology bachelors' program of the University of Graz. The study was approved by the local ethics committee according to the standards of the Helsinki declaration.

2.2. Material

2.2.1. Screening

Prior to the experimental study, participants underwent a 2.5 h screening session. This session focused on participants' executive functions, cognitive abilities, mathematical skills and English proficiency. Participants executive functions were examined with the *Simon Task* (Bialystok et al., 2004), the *Task Switching Paradigm* (Popescu et al., 2023) and the verbal and figural versions of the *Complex Span Task* (Meier et al., 2021). General cognitive abilities (e.g., intelligence) were tested using the *Berliner Intelligenzstrukturtest* (Berlin Intelligence Structure Test, BIS-4, Jäger et al., 1997). Mathematical and arithmetic skills were assessed using the *Mathematiktest für die Personalauswahl* (Mathematics Test for Personal Selection, Jasper & Wagener, 2013), and an *Arithmetic Fluency Task* by Vogel et al. (2017). The *Cambridge General English Questionnaire* (Cambridge University Press and Assessment, n.d.) and the *LexTale* (Lemhöfer & Broersma, 2012) were used to assess participants' English language level, whilst the *Bilingual Language Profile* (BLP, Birdsong et al., 2012) quantified their bilingual language dominance between German and English by creating a bilingual dominance spectrum. This spectrum spans from a potential minimum of -218 to a potential maximum of $+218$, with -218 signifying sole English language dominance, $+218$ sole German language dominance and 0 perfectly balanced bilingual language dominance between German and English. Additionally the screening included the *Abbreviated Math Anxiety Scale* (AMAS-G, Schillinger et al., 2018), and the *Neo-FFI* for assessing the Big Five personality traits (Kanning, 2009).

2.2.2. Measure of declarative arithmetic knowledge

To assess LSC in participants' declarative arithmetic knowledge, the *Box Arithmetic* (Hahn et al., 2019; Hahn et al., 2025) was utilized. Here participants were shown an arithmetic problem in the form of a two-digit number, the symbol “■”, and a single-digit number. The correct result was a random two-digit number that could not be calculated using typical operands (e.g., “seventeen ■ three = thirty-eight”). During the training sessions, each trial began with a 500 ms fixation cross in the middle of the screen. After this fixation, participants saw one Box

Calculation in the middle of the screen and both the correct answer and a distractor solution in the bottom left and right corner of the screen (location of correct solution was randomized). The distractor was randomly generated by either adding or subtracting the numbers one, two or ten to/from the correct result. Participants then had to indicate the correct answer using the arrow keys. The problem was shown until an answer was given or, for a maximum of ten seconds. After each problem, participants were asked to report their solution strategy using the corresponding number keys ("1. solution calculated", "2. solution retrieved", "3. other solution"; for more details on the response options see section 2.3.1). After this strategy self-report, participants were given

feedback regarding the correctness of their answer to the previous arithmetic problem (correct or not plus the correct answer). This screen was visible until the space bar was pressed, after which a new trial began (see Fig. 2a). The test sessions mirrored the training sessions with the difference, that after each strategy report, participants were also asked to self-report their translation processes (translation self-report). Lastly participants did not receive feedback regarding the correctness of their answers during the test sessions (see Fig. 2d).

2.2.3. Measure of procedural arithmetic knowledge

To assess the potential influence of LSC on participants procedural

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the arithmetic tasks. (a) Trial scheme of the training Sessions during the Box Arithmetic (Declarative arithmetic knowledge) Block. (b) Trial scheme of the training Sessions during the Pound Arithmetic (Procedural arithmetic knowledge) Block. (c) Trial scheme of the Testing Sessions during the Box Arithmetic (Declarative arithmetic knowledge) Block. (d) Trial scheme of the testing Sessions during the Pound Arithmetic (Procedural arithmetic knowledge) Block.

Fig. 2. (continued).

arithmetic knowledge, the Pound Arithmetic (Rickard, 1997) was utilized. In the Pound Arithmetic, participants were shown an arithmetic problem in the form of a single-digit number (A) and a two-digit number (B), connected by the operand #, which resulted in another two-digit number (e.g., three # seventeen = thirty-four). This problem could be solved by using the algorithm $2B - A + 3$. Participants were shown this correct algorithm for solving the Pound Arithmetic every 10 trials in a verbal form corresponding with their language of training. As shown in Fig. 2b, the trial sequence was similar to the training of arithmetic facts, with the exception that every problem was presented for a maximum of 20s instead of 10s. This was done because the execution of the calculation procedure required more time than retrieving the answer from memory. The training was also similar in regard to the strategy self-reports and the feedback participants received. The test trials mirrored the training trials of the arithmetic procedure training, substituting the feedback after every trial with the aforementioned translation self-report. Additionally, participants did not receive further reminders of the algorithm of solving the Pound Arithmetic (see Fig. 2d).

2.2.4. Measure of number reading speed

To counteract the unintended influence of training on participants' number reading speed in the language of training, we presented participants with an additional training of number reading speed in their unused language. This intentional training was applied at the end of each training session. To train number reading speed in the unused language of training, participants were presented with a total of 28 number-words in said language, ten of which being *pseudo* (non-existent) number-words. Each trial began with a 500 ms fixation, after which participants were presented with either a real or pseudo number-word. This stimulus was visible for a maximum of 10s or until participants answered via key press, whether the given word was a real number-word or not, after which their reaction time was recorded. After answering, participants were given visual feedback on the correctness of their answer. In addition to this training, we also recorded participants' reading speed in both German and English at the end of the posttest and all three follow up time points. The assessment in reading speed mirrored the training of reading speed, with participants first being

assessed in their language of training, followed by their non-training Language. In addition, during the assessment participants did not receive visual feedback regarding the correctness of their answers anymore.

2.3. Procedure

2.3.1. Training procedure

Participants underwent four days of training, followed by a posttest session on the fifth day and three follow-up tests: one week, one month and three months after the end of the training. The first training session and all test sessions (posttest and three follow-ups) were conducted in a laboratory. The second, third and fourth training session were done by participants at home, using *PsychoPy's Pavlovia* extension (Peirce et al., 2019). To ensure participants take part in the at-home training, they received a minimum of one reminder every day, plus additional individual reminders as needed, based on a regular check done by the researchers. The training sessions included the two arithmetic trainings drawing on fact and procedural knowledge accompanied by the training of number-word reading speed. Participants were randomly assigned to one of two groups. One group was trained using German (their L1), whilst the other group received the instructions in English (their L2). Special care was taken that the language of training was enforced as much as possible. Specifically, all instructions and interactions with the participants took place in the language of training, in line with the recommendations for bilingual education made by Grosjean (1998). Most importantly, numbers were presented in the form of verbal number-words (e.g., “seventy-two”, “thirty-five”, ...), similar to previous studies on LSC (e.g., Volmer et al., 2018).

Around half of the participants in each group (English: 29, German: 32) started with the Box Arithmetic (declarative knowledge) whereas the other half (English: 31, German: 30) started with the Pound Arithmetic (procedural knowledge). Participants were assigned randomly to these two orders. In the Box Arithmetic block, participants were taught artificial arithmetic facts. Here, participants were presented with six different Box problems, with each problem being shown eight times per session, resulting in a total of 48 trials per session (see Fig. 2a). In the Pound Arithmetic block participants worked on a total of 76 trials per session. These trials were split up in 36 novel trials each session, making up the Novel Arithmetic Procedure block, whilst the other 40 trials made up the so-called Novel Arithmetic Fact block. In this Novel Arithmetic Fact block, five randomly chosen Pound Arithmetic problems were repeated eight times per session over the course of the whole training, whereas all the other problems were repeated only once. Participants could increasingly store these five high-frequent-repeating items as novel arithmetic facts and solve them using fact retrieval. This procedure served to create a measure of declarative arithmetic knowledge, which approximates the transition from procedural to fact knowledge that typically occurs in arithmetic knowledge acquisition in childhood. The other 36 trials were different problems which were randomly chosen from a list of 144 calculations, making sure no two calculations were repeated during training (see Fig. 2b). After each trial of both blocks, participants were asked to self-report their solution strategy by selecting one of three options using the corresponding number keys. The options were: “1. solution calculated” (the solution was achieved by calculating at least part of the problem), “2. solution retrieved” (the solution was achieved purely by retrieval from memory) and “3. other solution” (the solution was achieved using other strategies like guessing, randomly answering, accidentally hitting the wrong key, etc.). The strategy self-report was kept uniform over both types of arithmetic tasks to reduce cognitive load and was used as a manipulation check. After both tasks have been finished, participants went through the training of reading speed of their non-instructed language.

2.3.2. Test procedure

On the fifth day of the training week, as well as on the three follow-

up time points, participants were invited back to the lab for the test sessions. Participants again randomly started with one of the arithmetic task blocks. The trial schemata were similar to the training procedure, except that one half of the problems were presented in German, whilst the other half was presented in English. Instead of receiving feedback, participants were asked to self-report their translation processes (translation self-report), which they used to solve each item (see Fig. 2c and d). This self-report format was inspired by the one used by Hahn et al. (2025), allowing for the following answers: “1. translated into trained language”, “2. translated into numbers” or “3. no translation”. Similar to the previously mentioned strategy report, the translation self-report was the same for all tasks, irrespective of the task language, in order to reduce cognitive load during the test. At the end of the posttest session, participants had to work through the aforementioned reading test. Participants were presented with two sets of number-words (one German, one English) starting with the language, which they already practiced in the number training. For each of these sets, participants were presented a total of ten pseudo number-words and 18 real number-words, bringing the overall trial count of the number test up to 56 (28 each). The preregistered version of the study can be found on the OSF under the following link: <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/EG4W8>

3. Results

All statistical analyses were done in R (R Core Team, 2021) using the coding environment RStudio (Posit team, 2025).

3.1. Analyses of participants' L2 proficiency and number reading speed

Analysis of Participants L2 data acquired during the preliminary screening showed that participants were on average more dominant in their L1 ($M = 99.96$, $SD = 31.23$). The only exception were two participants who, based on their results in the BLP, qualified as balanced bilinguals with scores of -5.55 and 0.09 respectively (Birdsong et al., 2012). Participants showed a mean Age of Acquisition in English of 7 years ($SD = 2$). The results of the L2 Tests indicated a mean English level of C1 according to the CEFR (Council of Europe, 2020) system (Cambridge General English Questionnaire: $M = 21$, $SD = 2.14$; LexTale: $M = 80.94$, $SD = 11.38$). To assess possible differences in L2 skill and bilingual dominance between the two groups, we calculated paired t -tests for each L2 assessment. The two groups did not show significant differences in their results of the LexTale ($t(118.96) = -0.18$, $p = .855$), the Cambridge General English Questionnaire ($t(119.38) = -0.38$, $p = .703$) and in their bilingual dominance ($t(101.66) = 1.18$, $p = .243$).

In the short assessments of number-word reading speed at the end of the posttest session, there were no group differences for English number-words ($t(120) = 0.82$, $p = .410$, $d = 0.15$; German Training: $M = 1140$ ms, $SD = 270$ ms; English Training: $M = 1030$ ms, $SD = 210$ ms). For German number-word reading speed there were significant differences between the two groups ($t(120) = 2.71$, $p < .001$, $d = 0.49$; German Training: $M = 960$ ms, $SD = 220$ ms; English Training: $M = 920$ ms, $SD = 270$ ms).

3.2. Manipulation check: strategy self-reports

As a manipulation check, we first analyzed participants' strategy self-reports in the posttest session by calculating the mean percentage of self-reports per solution strategy for correct trials, in each of the three tasks based on the corresponding switching condition. The switching condition reflects whether the language of encoding and retrieval differed (switch) or matched (no switch; see Table 1).

For the artificial arithmetic facts (Box Arithmetic), in the vast majority of trials participants reported to have directly retrieved the correct solution. The remaining strategy self-reports indicated mainly other strategies such as guessing, whereas calculations were (incorrectly) reported in only a very few trials. This is in line with the structure of our

Table 1

Descriptive data of the manipulation check split up by solution strategy and switching condition. All values are presented in percent.

Task	Calculated		Retrieved		Other	
	Switch	No Switch	Switch	No Switch	Switch	No Switch
Box	4.28	3.33	74.65	78.62	21.07	18.05
Pound	84.99	84.13	7.56	8.71	7.45	7.16
Procedures						
Pound Fact	55.96	53.21	38.63	42.40	5.41	4.39

material, given that the artificial equations could only be learned and retrieved as facts but never calculated.

The descriptive statistics of the procedural trials of the Pound Arithmetic showed the use of calculation in the vast majority of the trials, confirming our intention that this task relies on procedural knowledge.

Lastly the fact trials of the Pound Arithmetic show a mixture between self-reported calculation and retrieval strategies. This pattern indicates that the repetition of the selected Pound Arithmetic trials did not result in the acquisition of corresponding fact knowledge. Rather, the self-reports reveal that about half of the trials were solved through fact retrieval whereas the other half was solved by applying a calculation procedure. LSC occurring in this task cannot be directly associated with one of the two knowledge types. Therefore, we decided to omit further analyses on these trials and analyzed LSC only in the Box Arithmetic and the procedural trials of the Pound Arithmetic.

3.3. Language-Switching Costs in declarative and procedural knowledge

To analyze LSC in declarative and procedural arithmetic knowledge, two 2 × 2 Repeated Measures ANOVAs were calculated. These included the factors Switching (switch, no switch; referring to trials in the posttest session in which the language of encoding and retrieval differed or did not differ) and the Language of Training (German, English). This analysis also allows to test for potential directional effects of LSC (i.e., whether LSC are stronger when switching from L1 to L2 as compared to from L2 to L1). The descriptive statistics of the 2 × 2 ANOVA are presented in Table 2.

3.3.1. LSC in declarative arithmetic knowledge (Box Arithmetic)

In the 2 × 2 ANOVA for reaction times in the Box Arithmetic task, we observed only a main effect of Switching ($F(1,120) = 77.04, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.391$), revealing that participants responded slower in the switching compared to the non-switching trials. The main effect of Language of Training ($F(1, 120) = 1.67, p = .199, \eta_p^2 = 0.014$) and the interaction between Switching and Language of Training ($F(1, 120) = 1.05, p = .308, \eta_p^2 = 0.009$) were not significant.

For accuracies, there were no significant effects: Switching ($F(1, 120) = 3.75, p = .055, \eta_p^2 = 0.030$), Language of Training ($F(1, 120) = 0.37, p = .542, \eta_p^2 = 0.003$), Switching x Language of Training interaction ($F(1, 120) = 3.75, p = .055, \eta_p^2 = 0.030$). Thus, for arithmetic facts, we detected LSC in reaction times in both languages of training, but not

Table 2

Descriptive data of the Box Arithmetic and Pound Arithmetic tasks at the Test (first posttest) time point. Accuracies (Acc) are presented in percentages. Reaction times (RT) are milliseconds.

Task		Switch		No Switch	
		M	SD	M	SD
Box Arithmetic	Acc	78.55	17.73	81.45	13.84
	RT	3713	1117	3069	895
Pound Arithmetic	Acc	86.75	12.03	89.44	11.50
	RT	6815	1842	7436	2046

in accuracies.

3.3.2. LSC in procedural arithmetic knowledge (Pound Arithmetic)

In the procedural trials of the Pound Arithmetic task, we found a main effect of Switching in the participants' reaction times ($F(1, 120) = 35.66, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.229$). Here participants responded slower in switching compared to non-switching trials. No main effects of Language of Training ($F(1, 120) = 0.17, p = .680, \eta_p^2 = 0.001$), nor a significant interaction between Switching and Language of training emerged ($F(1, 120) = 1.36, p = .245, \eta_p^2 = 0.011$).

Focusing on participants' accuracies, we observed a main effect of Switching ($F(1, 120) = 9.38, p = .003, \eta_p^2 = 0.072$). Participants answered significantly more correctly in non-switching items compared switching items. Again, no main effects of Language of Training ($F(1, 120) = 0.55, p = .461, \eta_p^2 = 0.005$) emerged and the interaction between Switching and Language of Training did not turn out significant ($F(1, 120) = 3.57, p = .061, \eta_p^2 = 0.029$). Thus, in contrast to the declarative arithmetic knowledge, in procedural arithmetic knowledge LSC emerged in both reaction times and accuracies. Again, the language of training did not moderate these effects.

3.4. Stability of Language-Switching Costs

To examine the stability of LSC over time, we analyzed participants' performance across the posttest session and the three follow-up sessions for both tasks. To this end we calculated two additional 2 × 3 Repeated Measures ANOVAs. These included the factor Switching and the factor Session ("Test", "Follow-up 1", "Follow-up 2" and "Follow-up 3"). Since LSC in the posttest session were independent of the language of training and for the sake of simplicity, we decided to exclude the factor Group in the following analyses. Importantly, due to participant drop-out across the follow-up test sessions, the analyses were conducted with 74 participants.

3.4.1. Stability of LSC in declarative arithmetic knowledge (Box Arithmetic)

In this 2 × 4 ANOVA on reaction times in the Box Arithmetic (see Fig. 3a), we observed significant main effects of Switching ($F(1, 73) = 36.11, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.331$) and session ($F(3, 219) = 12.08, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.142$), as well as a significant interaction between these two variables ($F(3, 219) = 6.66, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.084$). Post hoc analyses including Bonferroni corrections showed significant LSC in all four sessions, even though they slightly varied in size: Posttest: $t(73) = -6.27, p < .001, d = -0.73$; Follow-up 1: $t(73) = -5.16, p < .001, d = -0.60$; Follow-up 2: $t(73) = -3.33, p = .038, d = -0.39$; Follow-up 3: $t(73) = -4.66, p < .001, d = -0.55$.

For accuracies, the main effect of Switching ($F(1, 73) = 3.39, p = .070, \eta_p^2 = 0.044$) and the interaction between Switching and Session were not significant ($F(3, 219) = 0.81, p = .488, \eta_p^2 = 0.011$). Only a main effect of Session was observed ($F(3, 219) = 6.05, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.076$). Post hoc analyses revealed these differences to be between the Follow-up 1 ($M = 0.84, SD = 0.14$) and Follow-up 2 ($M = 0.8, SD = 0.15$) sessions ($t(73) = 3.29, p = .009, d = 0.38$), as well as between the Follow-up 1 ($M = 0.84, SD = 0.14$) and Follow-up 3 ($M = 0.79, SD = 0.15$) sessions ($t(73) = 3.91, p = .001, d = 0.46$).

3.4.2. Stability of LSC in procedural arithmetic knowledge (Pound Arithmetic)

The analysis of reaction times in the procedural trials of the Pound Arithmetic task across the four test-sessions resulted in a significant main effect of Switching ($F(1, 73) = 17.69, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.195$). The main effect of Session ($F(3, 219) = 0.72, p = .539, \eta_p^2 = 0.010$) and the interaction between Switching and Session ($F(3, 219) = 2.43, p = .066, \eta_p^2 = 0.032$) were not significant (see Fig. 3b). Hence, LSC did not significantly change over time.

In accuracies, no main effect of Switching ($F(1, 73) = 0.03, p = .865,$

Fig. 3. Analysis of stability of LSC. (a) Stability of LSC for declarative arithmetic knowledge (reaction times). (b) Stability of LSC for procedural arithmetic knowledge (reaction times).

$\eta_p^2 < 0.001$) nor an interaction with Session ($F(3, 219) = 1.74, p = .159, \eta_p^2 = 0.023$) emerged. Only a main effect of Session was found ($F(3, 219) = 5.44, p = .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.069$). Post hoc analyses showed these

differences to be between the Follow-up 1 ($M = 0.92, SD = 0.1$) and Follow-up 2 ($M = 0.88, SD = 0.14$) timepoints ($t(73) = 3.28, p = .010, d = 0.38$), as well as between the Follow-up 1 ($M = 0.92, SD = 0.1$) and

Fig. 4. Translation self-reports at the time of testing - Declarative arithmetic knowledge (Box Arithmetic).

Follow-up 3 ($M = 0.87, SD = 0.13$) timepoints ($t(73) = 4.73, p < .001, d = 0.55$).

3.5. Associations of Language-Switching Costs with individual differences

To examine the moderating role of individual differences on the extent of LSC, we analyzed Pearson correlations between individual LSC and individual difference data gathered in the screening session. Given the large number of correlations (31) we applied FDR corrections. Individual LSC in reaction times were calculated by subtracting the mean reaction time in the non-switching condition from their mean reaction time in the corresponding switching condition. This was done separately for both tasks. After corrections for multiple comparisons using FDR, we did not detect any significant correlations (see Table A1). All bivariate correlations were smaller than 0.18.

3.6. Translation self-reports

Finally, to gain insights into the cognitive processes related to LSC, we calculated 2×2 ANOVAs with the factors Language of Training (German, English) and Switching (switch, no switch) on the mean percentages of self-reported translations into the trained language and into numbers.

3.6.1. Translation self-reports in the declarative arithmetic knowledge task (Box Arithmetic)

In the Box Arithmetic task (see Fig. 4), for translation into trained language, main effects for both Switching ($F(1, 116) = 95.25, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.451$) and Language of Training ($F(1, 116) = 5.02, p = .027, \eta_p^2 = 0.041$) were observed. In addition, we found an interaction between

Switching and Language of Training ($F(1, 116) = 9.28, p = .003, \eta_p^2 = 0.074$). Post hoc analyses revealed that both the German and English training groups translated significantly more often into their trained language in switching trials than in the no-switching trials (English: $t(116) = 9.06, p < .001, d = 1.35$; German: $t(116) = 4.75, p < .001, d = 0.71$). In addition the percentage of self-reported language translations in switching trials was higher in the English group, compared to the German group ($t(116) = 2.8, p = .036, d = 0.66$).

For translations into numbers, we found a main effect of Switching ($F(1, 116) = 11.22, p = .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.088$), but no main effect of Language of Training ($F(1, 116) = 0.91, p = .342, \eta_p^2 = 0.008$), nor a significant interaction ($F(1, 116) = 0.80, p = .374, \eta_p^2 = 0.007$). Across both groups, in 22.98% of the switching trials participants reported translations into numbers, as compared to 15.51% of the non-switching trials.

These findings indicate that LSC in the Box Arithmetic drawing on declarative arithmetic knowledge are associated with translations both into the trained language and into numbers with a larger effect for language translations.

3.6.2. Translation self-reports in the procedural arithmetic knowledge task (Pound Arithmetic)

In the Pound Arithmetic (see Fig. 5), for translations into the trained language, a main effect of Switching ($F(1, 116) = 38.34, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.248$), as well as an interaction between Language of Training and Switching ($F(1, 116) = 16.62, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = 0.125$) emerged. The main effect of Language of Training was not significant ($F(1, 116) = 1.74, p = .190, \eta_p^2 = 0.015$). Only in the German training group, switching compared to no-switching was associated with a higher percentage of self-reported translations into the trained language ($t(116) = 4.44, p < .001, d = 0.82$). In the English training group, this strategy was reported

Note. Stars indicate significance.
 * $p < .05$
 ** $p < .01$
 *** $p < .001$
 Error bars indicate ± 1 SE of the mean.

Fig. 5. Translation reports at the time of testing - Pound Arithmetic: Procedural Task.

similarly often in both conditions ($t(116) = 1.5, p = .825, d = 0.21$). Additionally, the German group reported language translations in the switching condition more often than the English group ($t(116) = -2.73, p = .044, d = -0.61$).

For translations into numbers, only the main effect of Language of Training was significant ($F(1, 116) = 5.90, p = .017, \eta_p^2 = 0.048$). Independently of language switching, translations into numbers were reported more often in the English (50.35%) compared to the German training group (33.65%). The other effects were not significant (Switching: $F(1, 116) = 1.80, p = .183, \eta_p^2 = 0.015$; Group*Switching: $F(1, 116) = 0.81, p = .369, \eta_p^2 = 0.007$).

Thus, similar to the artificial arithmetic facts trials, LSC are associated with self-reported language translations but now only in the German training condition. Translations into numbers occur generally more frequently compared to language translation, but are not moderated by language switching.

4. Discussion

The main goal of our study was to further our understanding of language-dependent knowledge representations in arithmetic learning. More specifically, we investigated whether LSC emerge not only in declarative but also in procedural arithmetic knowledge. Moreover, we aimed to find out how stable these LSC are across repeated assessments over three months and if individual differences correlate with them. Finally, we sought to provide new insights into the application of translation processes into the trained language and into numbers.

4.1. LSC in declarative arithmetic knowledge

We observed LSC in participants' reaction times in the Box Arithmetic task, which replicates previous findings on the existence of LSC in declarative arithmetic knowledge (Grabner et al., 2012; Saalbach et al., 2013; Volmer et al., 2018). This holds particularly true for studies by Hahn et al. (2025, 2019), who introduced the Box Arithmetic into this research and also reported LSC in reaction times but not in accuracy. A notable difference between the studies by Hahn et al. and the present one lies in the experimental design. While Hahn et al. presented the problems auditorily to the participants, we used written number-words, like most of the previous studies in this field. Therefore, our findings demonstrate that LSC occur in this type of artificial arithmetic problems in both modalities (auditory and visual).

4.2. LSC in procedural arithmetic knowledge

More importantly, LSC emerged also in the procedural trials of the Pound Arithmetic, both in reaction times and accuracies. Participants answered more slowly in those trials, in which the languages of training and testing differed. In addition, they made more mistakes, even though the high average accuracy of 89.44% in the no-switching trials indicates that the new procedure was well learned during the four-day training. Our observation of LSC in procedural arithmetic knowledge is a novel finding for the field of LSC research and stands in contrast to our prediction based on the Triple Code Model frameworks (Dehaene & Cohen, 1995; Lachelin et al., 2023; Siemann & Petermann, 2018) that LSC only emerge for declarative arithmetic knowledge. In these theoretical models, it is assumed that the execution of arithmetic procedures relies less strongly on the Auditory Verbal Word Frame. Rather, the execution of exact arithmetic procedures as in our Pound Arithmetic task is assumed to involve the Analogue Magnitude Representation, which is regarded to be largely language-independent (Dehaene et al., 1999; Dehaene & Cohen, 1995; Siemann & Petermann, 2018). Thus, the present finding suggests that both arithmetic facts and procedures are stored in a language-dependent way.

4.3. Directionality of LSC

In both tasks, LSC were not moderated by the language of training, despite a group difference in the assessed number reading speed for German number words. In other words, LSC were equally strong when switching from L1 to L2 and switching from L2 to L1. This finding of non-directionality in declarative arithmetic knowledge does not align with the prediction of the BTM of faster translations from L2 to L1, and consequently, smaller LSC. However, even though the BECM also includes the prediction of an asymmetric spread of activation between the stronger (verbal code in L1) and weaker code (verbal code in L2), the present finding of non-directionality in the Box Arithmetic task can be attributed to a strong training effect in L2. The repeated training may have strengthened the associations between problems and their solutions in L2 to the extent that the retrieval efficiency for the Box Arithmetic problems became independent of the general language dominance (see also Martinez-Lincoln et al., 2015). Nonetheless, as outlined in the introduction, the evidence on the directionality of LSC remains mixed, with some studies observing it (e.g., Saalbach et al., 2013) and others not (e.g., Hahn et al., 2019). Thus, additional studies are needed to systematically examine variables that moderate the directionality of LSC in both declarative and procedural arithmetic knowledge.

4.4. Stability of LSC

The LSC in participants' reaction times were stable in both tasks across multiple test sessions over three months. This again describes a novel finding. In both tasks, LSC in reaction times could be observed not only in the posttest session on the day after the end of the training but also one week, one month and three months afterwards (although with a reduced sample size due to dropouts). As shown in Fig. 3a and b, while in the Box Arithmetic the absolute size of LSC does not notably differ between the different measurement time points, in the Pound Arithmetic there is some non-significant decline in LSC over time. It may be speculated that this decline derives from the creation of novel or stronger mental representations in the non-trained language through the repeated exposure to arithmetic problems in both languages. Additionally, due to the use of multiple domains of arithmetic processing in procedural arithmetic knowledge, it could be speculated that these novel or stronger mental representations get created more quickly in procedural arithmetic knowledge compared to declarative arithmetic knowledge, leading to this result pattern. Irrespective of this slight decline, the finding of stable LSC for both declarative and procedural arithmetic knowledge over three months despite repeated exposure to the tasks in both languages, is of high theoretical and practical relevance. It shows that already after a few days of training, a knowledge representation in one language can be established that persists over time despite subsequent practice in both languages. However, it remains an open question to what extent and in what time a more intense practice or even a targeted training can reduce the LSC for both knowledge types.

4.5. Individual differences in LSC

LSC in both tasks were not associated with any of the individual characteristics assessed in our screening. Whether this is due to these associations simply not existing or if it is a case of using not the right tools for assessing relevant characteristics cannot be determined with the present data. Due to this, our results lead us to the conclusion that LSC are a general phenomenon that affects individuals independently of their domain-general and domain-specific competencies.

4.6. Translation tendencies in learners

Finally, the analyses of the translation self-reports revealed that language-switching was predominantly associated with a higher self-reported use of translations into the trained language rather than into

numbers. This provided us with further insights into the type of translation processes associated with language switching. Hahn et al. (2025) were the first to use trial-by-trial translation self-reports in an experimental study on LSC. After each problem, they asked participants whether they translated any numbers during problem solving and found that language switching in solving artificial and actual arithmetic fact problems was related to a higher number of self-reported translations as compared to the no-switching condition. This was in line with their hypothesis that LSC are primarily caused by additional translation processes. In the present study, we extended their procedure by asking participants whether they translated into the trained language or into numbers (or did not translate at all).

In the Box Arithmetic task, we found that language-switching was associated with a higher number of language translations and – to a smaller extent – a higher number of translations into numbers. The first result is in line with Hahn et al.'s findings who also administered the Box Arithmetic task. That is, participants mainly relied on translation processes when required to solve artificial arithmetic problems in a different language. The additional interaction effect revealed that switching into the trained language was more frequent in the English training group (i.e., from L2 to L1) than in the German training group (i.e., from L1 to L2). This pattern fits both the BECM and the BTCM. In the BECM, it would be conceptualized as an involvement of code conversion processes in the language-switching condition. In the BTCM, it matches the expected language translation processes within the Auditory Verbal Word Frame. The directionality of self-reported language translations stands in contrast to the reaction time findings but is in line with the predictions of both models. It may reflect that conversion or translation processes from L2 to L1 are not faster but occur more frequently compared to the other direction. The higher frequency of translation into a numeric form in the switching (22.98%) compared to the non-switching trials (15.51%) can be understood based on the (B)ECM, that is, participants relied more strongly on the most efficient Arabic digit pathway in the demanding language-switching condition.

In the Pound Arithmetic task, language switching was accompanied only by self-reported translations into the trained language in the German training group. This finding extends the results by Hahn et al. (2025, 2019): language translations during a procedural task depend on the switching direction. That is, translations are reported more frequently when switching from L1 to L2 compared to switching from L2 to L1. Participants who were trained in their L2 preferred the translation into numbers when solving procedural problems, in both switching and non-switching conditions. These findings support the assumptions of the BTCM that the ability to access one's knowledge depends on the skill in the language of acquisition. If the procedural knowledge was acquired in one's L2 (i.e., the less proficient language), a secondary domain – the Visual Arabic Number Form – seems to be needed for problem solving, irrespective of the language of testing. Contrarily, if procedural knowledge was acquired in L1, the Visual Arabic Number Form is needed to a lesser extent, and in the case of language switching, the verbal representation in the Auditory Verbal Word Frame becomes more important.

4.7. Limitations and future directions

The first limitation of the present study concerns the fact trials of the Pound Arithmetic. We repeated five problems of the Pound Arithmetic eight times per session so that participants could learn them as arithmetic facts and, consequently, solve problems in the test using fact retrieval. The strategy self-reports revealed that this manipulation did not have the desired effect. In only about half the trials, the problems were reported to be retrieved from memory. Therefore, we decided to not further analyze LSC in these trials as they do not qualify as fact learning and, thus, building up declarative arithmetic knowledge representations. This issue was also reported by participants in the test sessions. Several participants mentioned that they started to calculate the result of a given fact item and whilst calculating they realized that

they already knew the answer. Consequently, they struggled in choosing the applied strategy (fact retrieval, calculation or other). It appears that eight repetitions of five items over four training sessions are not sufficient to store these facts in a way that they are always retrieved and/or to make participants aware of this fact knowledge. Hahn et al. (2025), who administered six repetitions of six problems over four training sessions, also found that participants reported procedural strategies in multiplication and subtraction fact problems on average between 10 and 18% of the trials, respectively.

The second limitation relates to the introduction of a new assessment of translation processes during the tests. In contrast to Hahn et al. (2025), who simply asked whether any numbers were translated, we differentiated between three options, (i.e., translated into trained language, translated into numbers, no translation). Some participants reported to be confused by these options, and the single-choice nature made it harder for them to come to a final decision after each trial. In future studies, participants could undergo a short metacognitive training using different types of problems, in addition to giving them the possibility to answer in a multiple-choice format.

The third limitation concerns the findings related to the stability of LSC. These findings do not only reflect time-related effects. They are confounded with the repeated exposure to the test items in both languages. On the one hand, because of this confound we do not know the extent of LSC when tested at different time points after the end of the training in one language. To answer this question, we would have needed different groups within each training language that are tested at different time points afterwards. On the other hand, our procedure has a higher ecological validity. It would appear unusual to being instructed in one language for a given time period and then being required to retrieve or apply this knowledge in another language after, for instance, three months. Thus, our procedure shows the stability of LSC over time and repeated knowledge retrieval in both languages.

Lastly, we did not detect any correlations between various individual characteristics and participants' LSC in the different tasks. Our findings indicate that individual characteristics may not play a strong role, but our sample might not have had sufficient power to detect subtle individual differences.

4.8. Conclusion

In conclusion, the finding of LSC in both task types demonstrates language-dependent knowledge representations in both declarative and procedural arithmetic knowledge. The translation self-reports further corroborate the involvement of language-specific representations. In contrast to some previous findings, LSC were non-directional, i.e., equally strong from L1 to L2 as from L2 to L1. This finding challenges predictions of both the Bilingual Triple Code Model (Lachelin et al., 2023) and the Bilingual Encoding Complex Model (Bernardo, 2001). Both models predict higher LSC when switching from L1 to L2 as compared to switching from L2 to L1. The non-directional LSC in the latter model could be explained by a strong training effect in L2. LSC were temporally stable and not moderated by individual differences in a wide range of variables, from executive functions to language proficiency to numerical abilities. Overall, the results from our laboratory experiment provide further insights into the language-dependency of knowledge representations in arithmetic. These insights are also of relevance for bilingual learning settings that become more and more important in our globalized society.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Kevin M. Baumschlager: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Moritz Wußing:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Cornelia Pachner:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation,

Conceptualization. **Henrik Saalbach**: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Lennart Schalk**: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Bert De Smedt**: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Roland H. Grabner**: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Appendix A. Analysis of associations of Language-Switching Costs with individual differences

Table A1

Correlation analysis of individual difference data gathered in the preliminary screening and participants' switching scores in the different task types.

Measure	Artificial Arithmetic Fact Switching	Novel Arithmetic Procedure Switching
Bilingual Dominance Score	0.15 (0.106)	0.02 (0.819)
Age of Acquisition (German)	-0.05 (0.551)	-0.05 (0.583)
Age of Acquisition (English)	0.02 (0.866)	-0.04 (0.700)
LexTale Score	-0.11 (0.229)	-0.04 (0.628)
Cambridge General English Questionnaire Score	-0.15 (0.105)	-0.08 (0.364)
Simon Task Accuracy	-0.03 (0.780)	0.04 (0.681)
Simon Task RT	0.07 (0.493)	-0.05 (0.587)
Task Switching Paradigm Accuracy	-0.03 (0.789)	0.13 (0.198)
Task Switching Paradigm RT	-0.02 (0.868)	-0.00 (0.960)
Figural Complex Span Accuracy	0.15 (0.152)	-0.05 (0.589)
Figural Complex Span Sum Score	0.15 (0.152)	-0.05 (0.589)
Figural Complex Span Distractor Accuracy	0.06 (0.587)	0.13 (0.203)
Figural Complex Span Distractor RT	-0.07 (0.491)	0.16 (0.118)
Verbal Complex Span Accuracy	-0.10 (0.336)	0.11 (0.289)
Verbal Complex Span Sum Score	-0.10 (0.336)	0.11 (0.289)
Verbal Complex Span Distractor Accuracy	-0.00 (0.964)	-0.06 (0.579)
Verbal Complex Span Distractor RT	0.07 (0.513)	0.06 (0.549)
AMAS Score	-0.09 (0.324)	0.03 (0.775)
MPA Score	0.09 (0.312)	-0.05 (0.601)
AFT Score	-0.18 (0.055)	-0.12 (0.185)
Last Math Grade	-0.15 (0.099)	-0.02 (0.854)
General Intelligence	-0.06 (0.520)	0.04 (0.694)
Processing Capacity	-0.06 (0.512)	0.02 (0.848)
Verbal Intelligence	-0.05 (0.555)	0.07 (0.416)
Numeric Intelligence	-0.10 (0.300)	-0.05 (0.569)
Figural Intelligence	0.03 (0.759)	0.08 (0.403)
Neuroticism	0.05 (0.580)	-0.04 (0.683)
Extraversion	-0.11 (0.237)	-0.01 (0.905)
Openness	-0.03 (0.785)	-0.08 (0.372)
Agreeableness	-0.10 (0.297)	-0.01 (0.880)
Conscientiousness	0.04 (0.665)	-0.05 (0.591)

Data availability

Data is accessible through the attached OSF link. Code and research materials are also available in the same repository.

Open Science Framework [Bilingual_Math_Dilemma_Data_final.csv](#) under the Folder "Data" (Original data)

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